

Kostić, Larisa, 0000-0001-7184-9966

Institute for Literature and Art, Belgrade

Lalatović, Jelena, 0000-0001-5293-2991

University of Zagreb, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences

FROM MANUSCRIPT TO METADATA: ADVANCING DIGITISING WORKFLOWS IN SERBIAN LITERARY RESEARCH

Introduction: The Legacy of Literary Criticism and Sub-digitisation

The Institute for Literature and Art is an independent research institution in the humanities, with a particular focus on literary history and theory, as well as a 60-year tradition. It was established by the Executive Council of the Republic of Serbia, the Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts, the Faculty of Philology at the University of Belgrade, and the University of Arts in Belgrade in 1962. However, the Institute remained organisationally independent of its founders, which meant that it established and maintained its autonomy in employment and research policies. As a result, the Institute's staff was granted the liberty to examine cultural phenomena at the verges of university curricula, encompassing non-canonical approaches to literary and cultural studies. This led to an expansion of the scope of literary theory at the Institute.

Today, the Institute has seven departments devoted to specific, narrower research fields:

- Periodicals in the History of Serbian Culture and Literature
- The History of Serbian Literary Criticism
- Literature and Cultural Self-awareness
- Comparative Research
- The Poetics of Modern and Contemporary Serbian Literature
- Theory of Literature and Art
- Folklore Studies

The bibliography published to mark the 60th anniversary of the Institute's work (Каталог издања 2022) showcases the Institute's research focus over the decades and highlights, among others, three specific interests:

- an emphasis on theoretical developments at home and abroad;
- a peculiar attentiveness to living classics of Yugoslav literature (Ivo Andrić and Miroslav Krleža) at that time (Каталог издања 2022, 5); and

- a curiosity for marginalised topics, such as women’s contributions to periodical cultures of the 19th and 20th centuries and the cultures of national minorities in Serbian territory.

As some of the most recent research at the Institute reveals, periodical cultures, a key example of such marginalised topics, turn out to be particularly fruitful for exploring mechanisms of oppression that often condense “the struggle to write” and “the struggle for rights” (Simić 2023).

A thorough analysis of the Institute’s bibliography, spanning over sixty years, reveals some persistent and intriguing continuities. For instance, in 1987, Svetlana Slapšak edited a volume dedicated to “trivial literature” (Slapšak 1987). Thirty-five years later, Bojan Jović and Tijana Tropin co-edited a volume on marginal and marginalised genres (Jović and Tropin 2022). Due to specific socio-historical circumstances, namely, the fact that modern Serbian culture (after 1918) developed in a post-imperial setting, which resulted in “combined and uneven development” (Anievas and Nişancioğlu 2015, 43–63), the relationship between the market and literature was shaped in a more conflictual manner than in fully modernised Western cultures. Mass print culture in Serbia, for example, emerged as late as the beginning of the 20th century, as indicated by the earliest studies in Serbian journalism (Skerlić 1911). Here, it is essential to acknowledge that the attribute “mass” in this context had a somewhat different meaning than usual. Illiteracy rates in the Kingdom of Serbia and later the Kingdom of Yugoslavia remained extremely high (up to 80% in certain regions; Tomich 1963) until the establishment of the Federal People’s Republic of Yugoslavia in 1946. This means that, although significant market development had occurred by the mid-20th century, there was no palpable mass consumption compared to the overall agrarian population. These circumstances, including a relatively fragile marketplace, created a cultural space without clear distinctions between popular, mass, trivial, and marginalised literature. Slapšak’s 1987 volume on trivial literature demonstrated how socially engaged readings, such as Marxist or feminist approaches, could substantially contribute to the reevaluation of specific authors, often women. Innovative methodologies, therefore, have the power to reframe and recategorise the interpretation of historical material. This implies that researchers are responsible for recontextualising the multilayered meanings and intersections between what is considered trivial, mass, popular, and marginalised when dealing with socially and culturally sensitive material. The later volume on marginal and marginalised genres, published in 2022, continued that practice.

Metadata Standardisation and Discoverability

The transition to the EPrints platform significantly improved metadata structuring and searchability. On the previous Islandora system, metadata entries were flexible but inconsistent. For instance, author names and titles entered in Cyrillic script were neither exposed in machine-readable form nor indexed by global search engines such as Google or Google Scholar. As a result, even fully published items often remained invisible to international audiences. Moreover,

Islandora's architecture lacked embedded metadata fields compliant with international standards, leading to errors in search retrieval and limiting the discoverability of Serbian literary content.

EPrints, by contrast, implement metadata standards such as Dublin Core and MARC21, ensuring consistency and visibility across systems. Records deposited via EPrints expose structured bibliographic data (e.g., title, author, abstract, keywords) through embedded metadata tags and OAI-PMH harvesting protocols. Since the adoption of EPrints at the Institute (now hosted at dirikum.org.rs), search engines and academic indexes can retrieve records more reliably, even when those records are written in non-Latin scripts. This stands in contrast to the previous repository instance at ikum.unilib.rs, which lacked this level of interoperability. The new platform thus aligns with current expectations in the digital humanities, where rich metadata plays a critical role in enhancing transnational visibility, facilitating multilingual access, and ensuring digital preservation.

Scholarly Visibility and Citation Metrics

The former Islandora-based repository did not offer tools for monitoring citation counts, download statistics, or user engagement. Consequently, there was no mechanism to evaluate the impact of research or to adjust content strategies based on scholarly interest. Since transitioning to EPrints, these capabilities have become available. The platform includes IRStats2, a plugin that enables near real-time monitoring of repository activity, including the number of downloads, views, and document types accessed over time. For example, the IRStats2 interface provides monthly reports of item views and full-text downloads, and it visualises the distribution of these interactions across individual documents and across different sections of the repository. Such detailed analytics allow repository administrators and authors to identify usage trends and high-interest content within the collection.

These new metrics enable repository managers and authors to evaluate which publications receive the most attention and to adjust their metadata, licensing, and dissemination efforts accordingly. The repository also supports integration with ORCID and DOI systems, which helps track author-level contributions and interlink publications with external citation databases. Although precise citation comparisons between the old and new systems are unavailable due to the absence of prior data, the qualitative change in visibility is evident through the repository's enhanced indexing on platforms such as Google Scholar, along with improved metadata linkage in curated indexes. The provision of standardised metadata is not merely a technical upgrade but a precondition for academic discoverability and impact in digitally mediated scholarly communication.

User and Workflow Features

EPrints offers several user-oriented features that have significantly enhanced repository management at the Institute. Submission workflows are now semi-automated, and metadata validation processes are integrated into the platform. Unlike Islandora, where much of the metadata

curation and classification required manual correction and lacked batch processing capabilities, EPrints supports custom input forms, multilingual metadata fields, and role-based workflows for depositors, editors, and administrators.

One significant enhancement is the ability to generate persistent identifiers automatically and to export records in standardised formats (e.g., XML, MODS, RDF). Multilingual support is critical in the Serbian context, where documents are written in both Cyrillic and Latin scripts. Automated validation tools and structured metadata schemas help ensure that deposited content is consistent, accurate, and semantically rich. These features reduce the time and expertise required for repository maintenance, thereby increasing confidence in the reliability and interoperability of the archived content.

Digital Humanities and Infrastructure Alignment

The technological changes described here reflect broader shifts in the field of digital humanities, where infrastructures must support linguistic diversity, metadata interoperability, and open science. EPrints enables compliance with international interoperability protocols (e.g., OAI-PMH, COAR, OpenAIRE guidelines) and enhances the FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) of the Institute's scholarly outputs. By transitioning to this modern infrastructure, the Institute is not only archiving literary and cultural scholarship more effectively but also contributing to the development of regional best practices in digital archiving.

Cultural Hub of the Serbian Humanities as a Digital Patchwork

The authors of this paper have recently formulated a draft proposal that could lead to a comprehensive digital transformation of the Institute's content dissemination. This envisaged "Cultural Hub of the Serbian Humanities" project would enable researchers and academics to perform specific tasks entirely in the digital realm, thereby saving time and allowing access to bodies of information and data that would otherwise remain unavailable without comprehensive digitisation. The draft of this embryonic project, entitled "Cultural Hub of the Serbian Humanities," would establish a digital collection comprising seven sub-collections organised according to the Institute's seven departments. The key activity in the pilot phase would be the digitisation of six representative papers per department (approximately forty papers in total as an initial sample). The criteria for selecting these works would be twofold in theory: methodological exceptionalism and broader socio-cultural relevance of the work. However, in practice, these two categories often overlap. The platform hosting these collections would be bilingual (Serbian and English), significantly increasing the online visibility and accessibility of the Institute's heritage. Each paper in the collection would be OCR-processed and accompanied by an extended annotation to facilitate keyword searching.

This collection of sub-collections is conceived as operating under the sign of a "patchwork," functioning as a tessellation that "connects pre-existing informational nodes while acknowledging

them to be incommensurable” (Flanders 2014, 172). One evident advantage of the digitisation process is improved access: many papers published in the 20th century or the early 21st century are currently hard to obtain due to the small number of copies stored in restricted library collections. This situation is paradoxical because, although open access and copyright-free licensing have long been standard practices in Serbian academic publishing, the general lack of digitisation has meant that these scholarly results are often accessible only through physical copies. A digital collection would open up space for a closer examination of past research and allow a critical assessment of the reproducibility and applicability of its methods. Furthermore, once implemented, the “Cultural Hub of the Serbian Humanities” has the potential to directly impact current research workflows.

For instance, in this patchwork model, disparate information from different departments, each with its own rules, internal policies, and preferences, would be connected through shared metadata, specifically keywords. This approach could encourage researchers to reconceptualise the role of abstracts and keywords as containers of metadata rather than treating these components of the scholarly apparatus merely as a digest of the manuscript. In other words, it would attribute greater agency to both ends of a digitised text (the author and the reader) as scholars come to understand abstracts and keywords as primary tools for search and visibility, thereby adopting the perspective of the “end user.”

Conclusion

The adoption of EPrints has streamlined workflows and reinforced the Institute’s role as an active participant in scholarly communication, helping Serbian literature and cultural studies engage more dynamically with the international academic community. The platform supports the Institute’s distinctive research directions, from the preservation of marginalised voices and scholarship on gender studies to the study of national minorities’ contributions, by providing a robust digital infrastructure for interdisciplinary research. This, in turn, fosters deeper connections between Serbia’s literary heritage and global academic discourse.

The transition from Islandora to EPrints represents a significant step forward in preserving, accessing, and sharing Serbian literary research. This deliberate move was intended to adopt tools that better align with the Institute’s vision of making Serbian scholarship visible and relevant on the global stage. The change has already yielded tangible results, from improving metadata consistency to increasing the discoverability of the Institute’s research in international academic databases.

The “Cultural Hub of the Serbian Humanities” initiative is a natural continuation of this endeavour. By digitising key works and creating a bilingual platform, we aim to address the challenge of limited access to our publications while also rethinking how metadata (in this case, abstracts and keywords) can serve as a bridge between scholars. In addition to preserving the past, this project is fundamentally about creating a dynamic space where our literary heritage can inspire new connections and foster innovative research.

REFERENCES

- Anievas, Alexander & Nişancıoğlu, Kerem. 2015. *How the West Came to Rule: The Geopolitical Origins of Capitalism*. London: Pluto Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctt183pb6f.7>.
- Bankier, J. G., and Kenneth Gleason, eds. 2014. *Institutional Repository Software Comparison*. Paris: United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.
- Castagné, Michel. 2013. "Institutional Repository Software Comparison: DSpace, EPrints, Digital Commons, Islandora and Hydra." R. Graduate Research [Non-Thesis]. August 14. <http://dx.doi.org/10.14288/1.0075768>.
- Flanders, Julia. 2014. "Rethinking Collections." In *Advancing Digital Humanities. Research, Methods, Theory*, edited by Paul Longley Arthur and Katherine Bode. London: Palgrave MacMillan.
- Gobble, MaryAnne M. 2018. "Digital Strategy and Digital Transformation." *Research Technology Management* 61, no. 5: 66–68. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26586469>.
- Јовић, Бојан and Тијана Тропин, eds.. 2022. *Маргинални и маргинализовани жанрови у књижевности*. Београд: Институт за књижевност и уметност.
- Kingston, Paul W. 2001. "The Unfulfilled Promise of Cultural Capital Theory." *Sociology of Education* 74, 88–99. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2673255>.
- Maticki, Miodrag, Vesna Matović and Slobodanka Peković, eds. 2004. *Književnost na jezicima manjina u Podunavlju*. Beograd: Institut za književnost i umetnost.
- Матовић, Весна and Марија Циндори, eds. 1995. *Банатска периодика XIX и XX века*. Нови Сад—Београд: Матица српска—Институт за књижевност и уметност.
- Каталог издања 1961–2022*. 2022. Београд: Институт за књижевност и уметност.
- Пековић, Слободанка. 1990. "Женски часописи с почетка века." In *Прилози за историју српске књижевне периодике: споменица Драгиши Витошевићу*, edited by Александар Петров. Нови Сад—Београд: Матица српска—Институт за књижевност и уметност.
- Simić, Zorana. 2023. "Women Editors in Interwar Yugoslavia Between the Struggle to Write and the Struggle for Rights: Katarina Bogdanović and Paulina Lebl Albala." *Radovi Zavoda za hrvatsku povijest Filozofskoga fakulteta Sveučilišta u Zagrebu* 55, no.1: 246–264. <https://doi.org/10.17234/RadoviZHP.55.14>.
- Скерлић, Јован. 1911. *Историјски преглед српске штампе 1791–1911*. Београд: Српско новинарско удружење.
- Slapšak, Svetlana, ed. 1987. *Trivijalna književnost*. Beograd: Institut za književnost i umetnost.

Tomich, Vera. 1963. *Education in Yugoslavia and the new reform: the legal basis, organization, administration, and Program of the secondary schools*. Washington: U. S. Department of Health, Education, and Welfare.

Verma, Lakshmi and Nishanth Kumar. “Comparative Analysis of Open Source Digital Library. 2018. Softwares: A Case Study.” *DESIDOC Journal of Library & Information Technology* 38 (5): 361–368. doi: 10.14429/djlit.38.5.12425.